

MULTIPLE MYELOMA AND HELICOBACTER PYLORI INFECTION DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION

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Abstract

The article presents the results of studies using an invasive diagnostic method to determine the levels of IgG antibodies to Helicobacter pylori (H.pylori) infection in patients with multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality in comparison with patients with multiple myeloma of the Russian-speaking population residents of the Kyrgyz Republic(Kirghizia).

At the comparative characteristic in patients with multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality reveal negative in 49 % of cases, medium levels in 21% cases, high levels in 18% of cases and less often low levels of IgG antibodies to H.pylori infection compared to patients with multiple myeloma of the Russian-speaking population of residents of the Kyrgyz Republic(Kirghizia),detection negative in 51% of cases, low levels in 91% of cases, medium levels in 79% of cases, high levels in 82% of cases.

A study for levels IgG antibodies to H. pylori infection in patients with multiple myeloma allows early diagnosis of helicobacter infection identification in medical history(anamnesis) and clinical pathology of the gastrointestinal tract confirmed by esophagoduodenoscopy(EGD scopy)(gastritis, atrophic, erosive, erosive-ulcerative gastritis, steroid ulcers, gastric and duodenal ulcers), as well as timely transfer from tablet steroid preparations to intravenous administration, in parallel with basic targeted therapy conducts antibacterial therapy in combination with H2 - blockers, proton pump inhibitors, antacids, antihelicobacter metabiotics.

Timely receiving the regimen of targeted therapy and upon achieving remission in patients with multiple myeloma, important perform standard eradication therapy in combination with bacterial strains.

Thus, in oncohematological diseases, these studies at the current stage of detection of H.pylori infection with a preventive purpose in patients with multiple myeloma is a serious step and a reliable platform for studying immunogenetic and population characteristics, and identifying clinical and laboratory markers, the presence of infectious complications against the background of taking frequent, basic steroid drugs, polychemotherapy (PChT). As well as timely suspend patients with multiple myeloma, from conduct according to indications bone marrow autotransplantation.

In the treatment underlying disease and at the early stage of the disease the detection, and treatment of gastrointestinal pathology by the affected H.pylori infection will improve the duration of remission, and during remission, receiving standard modern eradication therapy will increase the life expectancy of patients with multiple myeloma.

Keywords: multiple myeloma, infection Helicobacter pylori, prevalence, treatment, prevention.

INTRODUCTION:

With the development and prevalence of a whole series of oncohematological diseases, great importance is attached to viruses and bacteria. Detectability of the organism of infection, in particular with the carriers of Helicobacter pylori (H.pylori) infection and in benign, malignant oncohematological diseases and in patients with multiple myeloma (MM) are important for the development of effective treatment and determination of disease prognosis.

Multiple myeloma (MM)– is chronic pathological B- cell lymphoproliferative, clonally-malignant disease of the blood system, arising at the level of the germinal center of the lymph nodes, without involvement of the lymph nodes and the main morphological substrate which is plasma cells in varying degrees of maturity and capable of producing structurally-homogeneous immunoglobulins IgA, IgG, IgD, IgE and light (κ, λ) chains[1].

Among oncohematological diseases, according to the classification of the World Health Organization (WHO,2001)[14], multiple myeloma belongs to peripheral B-cell lymphoid tumors, developing gradually, which evidence a low degree of its malignancy.

Patients with multiple myeloma occur in the population of 2-3 cases per 100,000 populations per year [13]. The incidence in Europe is 6 per 100,000 populations per year [8]. In the treatment of the underlying disease, Helicobacter pylori infection plays an important role in oncohematological diseases [2].

According to the International Recommendations of Maastricht-IV(2012) and Maastricht-V (2017) [11;12], timely diagnosis of Helicobacter pylori infection and their subsequent effective treatment have a significantly positive effect on the course and prognosis.

At the initial stage, the duration and depth of damage to the gastric mucosa plays a large role, then the onset of the inflammatory-pathological process and its

gradual transition to a chronic form (gastritis, atrophic, erosive, erosive-ulcerative gastritis, gastric ulcer, duodenum, medicinal gastritis, steroid ulcers), as well as in the development of the malignant tumor process "carcinogen for humans" by a factor deeply involved in the genesis of cancer, MALT-type stomach lymphomas.

With timely diagnosis disease of multiple myeloma and initiated targeted therapy, long-term courses of steroid, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory and chemopreparations lead to additional damage gastrointestinal tract.

To date, with timely diagnosis, have been proposed modern, effective scheme therapy and basic drugs for the treatment of H. pylori infection. The Current European Concepts in the Management of Helicobacter pylori Infection -The Maastricht Consensus Report (Maastricht-I) was discussed and adopted [4]. The Maastricht-I agreement establishes the basic agreements of the indication for eradication and recommends optimal treatment regimens. According to the recommendations of the Maastricht Agreements (consensus Maastricht-II), they are divided into mandatory and expedient, a quadrotherapy scheme has been proposed [5; 9] and consensus (Maastricht-III) [10] separate formulated provisions on the treatment of Helicobacter pylori infection have been added.

In this regard, the purpose of our study was to identify Helicobacter pylori infection, to determine the degree of gastrointestinal damage and treatment in patients with multiple myeloma residents of the Kyrgyz Republic (Kirghizia).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

From March 2014 to January 2024, the study group included - 43 patients (28 men, 15 women), with different stages of the course and immunochemical variants of multiple myeloma (MM) disease. Of these 13 patients of kirghiz nationality(4-women, men-9) and the control group consisted of patients multiple myeloma of the Russian-speaking population(mixed nation and different nationalities) residents of the Kyrgyz Republic(Kirghizia) -30 patients (women-11, men-19), aged 38 to 84 years, all patients is are citizens of the Kyrgyz Republic(Kirghizia).

The study was conducted on the basis of the Eurasian center of oncohematology, immunology and therapy, in the laboratory of St. Petersburg NIIIE and M named after Pasteur, in the laboratories of polyclinics, clinics in city Nursultan (Astana), Bishkek. All studies for Helicobacter pylori infection were conducted by consent of patients and on a paid basis.

Method determination levels of the amount antibodies of Ig G to Helicobacter pylori infection:

The method is based on enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), the result was expressed in international units. The test system "ImmunoComb II Helicobacter pylori IgG" was used. The results were assessed according to the scale attached to the test system. According to the level of antibodies, sera were divided into the corresponding groups. 0-19 U/ml-negative result, 20-39 U/ml-low level of antibodies, 40-90 U/ml - medium level of antibodies, 91-120 and more U/ml - high level of antibodies.

Statistical processing of the results obtained included the analysis of standard criteria. X²-square was used to assess the significance of differences in the occurrence of certain signs between the control group and patients with multiple myeloma. Determination of the "p" value corresponding to the found value. X²-square, was carried out according to a computer program, taking into account one degree of freedom. All mathematical calculations and general statistical analysis of the obtained studies were carried out using a personal computer using a software package for spreadsheets - "Microsoft-ExcelM Version 7.0 for Windows 95, for Windows-2010, Statistica-5.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

All patients had a list of studies(Table 1) and were diagnosed with multiple myeloma based on complaints, medical history(anamnesis), objective data, standard small and large criteria: in the presence of plasma cells in the bone marrow punctuate more than 10%, M-gradient(monoclonal protein) in the blood/or urine and osteodestructive lesions in the flat bones, the presence of increased immunoglobulin parameters[1;3], as well as according to the simplified and minimally unchanged diagnostic criteria proposed by the International Working Group for the Study of Myeloma IMWG[6;7].

Considering, that Helicobacter pylori infection exists in the normal life of the body and when we conduct studies to detect IgG antibodies to H.pylori infection in primary patients with disease multiple myeloma, in detailed, thorough surveys had in medical history(anamnesis) of chronic gastric pathologies in remission, clinical manifestations were noted in the form of discomfort in the epigastria region, heartburn, periodically manifestation of hoarseness of the voice (gastroesophageal syndrome), hungry and nocturnal pains in the epigastria region, when eating rough food and dyspeptic manifestations.

After the diagnosis of multiple myeloma was established, patients received targeted therapy depending on the stage of the disease, the immunochemical variant and the severity of the condition.

Study of patients with multiple myeloma	
Diagnostic list of studies	
1.	expanded general clinical complete blood count with platelet count
2.	general urine analysis (urinalysis)
3.	daily loss of protein in urine
4.	Bens-Jones protein in urine
5.	fractions total protein and its fractions in blood serum
6.	liver tests, transaminases (ALT, AST) in blood serum
7.	an HIV infection study
8.	serum creatinine and calcium in blood serum
9.	residual nitrogen and serum urea in blood serum
10.	β_2 serum microglobulin in blood serum
11.	radiography of the skull, chest organs
12.	radiography of the pelvic bones
13.	bone marrow examination (sternal puncture)
14.	IgA,IgM,IgG immunoglobulins according to IgD, IgE indications
15.	free lung immunoglobulins (k, λ) chains
16.	abdominal organs ultrasound (ultrasound)
17.	electrocardiogram(ECG)
18.	lactate dehydrogenase(LDG)
19.	C-reactive protein (CRP)
20.	determination of IgG antibodies to Helicobacter pylori infection
21.	esophagoduodenoscopy (EGD scopy)

In patients with multiple myeloma in the presence of a with IgG antibodies to H. pylori infection and in medical history(anamnesis) of gastrointestinal pathology confirmed by esophagoduodenoscopy(gastritis, atrophic, erosive, erosive -ulcerative gastritis, stomach ulcer and duodenum ulcer, medicinal gastritis, steroid ulcers) and the possibility of their exacerbation and complications, at the same time prescribed antibacterial

therapy in combination with H2 - blockers (De-nol, ranitidine, famotidine), proton pump inhibitors (esomeprazole, omeprazole), antacids (maalox, phosphalugel, almogel), and antihelicobacter metabiotic (helinorm).

Our research among patients with multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality by prevalence of Helicobacter pylori infection are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparative characteristics of IgG antibody levels to Helicobacter pylori infection in patients with multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality.

In a comparative characterization of the prevalence rate for determining the levels of IgG antibodies to Helicobacter pylori infection in patients with multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality of residents of the

Kyrgyz Republic(Kirghizia), Figure 1, shows, that negative levels are detected in 46% of cases, low levels in 8% of cases, medium levels in 23% of cases and high levels in 23% of cases.

In terms of significance of differences, it is noted that when comparing the frequency of prevalence among patients with multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality, negative ones are detected in 46% of cases

and medium, high in 23% of cases each and low levels of IgG antibodies to *Helicobacter pylori* infection are detected less often and have statistically significant differences, where $p < 0.005$.

Figure 2. Indicators content of levels antibody IgG to *Helicobacter pylori* infection in patients multiple myeloma of residents Kyrgyz Republic (Kirghizia).

Comparative characterization of IgG antibody levels to infection *Helicobacter pylori* in patients with multiple myeloma residents in the Kyrgyz Republic (Kirghizia), the data of which are presented in Figure 2, showed, that during our observation, the results of studies showed that negative levels are detected in patients with multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality in 49% of cases and in patients with multiple myeloma of the Russian-speaking population Kyrgyz Republic (Kirghizia) in 51% of cases.

Low levels antibodies of IgG to *H. pylori* infection among patients with multiple myeloma of the kirghiz nationality are determined in 9 % of cases and in patients with multiple myeloma of the Russian-speaking population of residents of Kyrgyz Republic (Kirghizia) in 91% of cases.

Medium levels antibodies of IgG to *H.pylori* infection are detected in patients with MM of the kirghiz nationality in 21% cases and of the Russian-speaking population of residents of Kyrgyz Republic (Kirghizia) in 79% of cases.

High levels antibodies of IgG to *H.pylori* infection are detected in patients with multiple myeloma of the kirghiz nationality in 18% of cases and of the Russian-speaking population of residents of Kyrgyz Republic (Kirghizia) in 82% of cases.

In the significance of the differences in patients with multiple myeloma of the kirghiz nationality, negative levels antibodies of IgG to *Helicobacter pylori* infection are detected in 49% of cases and low, medium, high levels are to a lesser degree often detected on comparison with the control group negative levels antibodies of IgG to *Helicobacter pylori* infection are detected in 51% of cases, low levels in 91% of cases, high levels in 82% of cases and have statistically significant differences, where $p < 0.005$.

CONCLUSIONS:

Thus, a study in a group of patients with multiple myeloma were carried out for timely detection *Helicobacter pylori* infection and comprehensive examination

during the initial treatment. The results of clinical data and laboratory indicators make it possible to diagnose and detect at an early stage latent carriage of *H.pylori* infection, as well as to suspect the disease in detailed surveys, which contributes to timely treatment.

Based on a diagnostic comparative assessment negative levels of IgG antibodies to *H.pylori* infection are detected among patients of multiple myeloma of kirghiz nationality in 46% of cases, medium in 23% of cases and high levels in 23% of cases, which have a significant impact on the course of the disease, prognosis of the disease and of great practical importance.

At the treatment main disease and to achieve a good effect from the polychemotherapy (PChT), according to indications conducted auto-transplantation of bone marrow and for increase the life expectancy, it is necessary to simultaneously investigate and treatment in patients multiple myeloma pathology of the gastrointestinal tract.

At the detection in analyses in patients with multiple myeloma, the presence of IgG antibodies to *Helicobacter pylori* infection, in a medical history (anamnesis) of gastrointestinal pathology, confirmed both clinically and esophagoduodenoscopy and the possibility of exacerbation and avoiding complications (ulcerative bleeding, secondary anemia, perforations, penetration), it is necessary to simultaneously and parallel prescribe antibacterial therapy in combination with H2-blockers, proton pump inhibitors, antacids, antihelicobacter metabiotics.

In the period of remission of the underlying disease, according to indications assign schedule modern eradication therapy.

FINDINGS:

1. The patients with multiple myeloma necessary be included in the list of studies to define the levels antibodies of IgG to *Helicobacter pylori* infection.

2. In the presence of *H. pylori* infection in patients with multiple myeloma, necessary to conduct gastro-

copy with taking from different maximum of 5 ulcerated areas of biopsy material and consultation of a gastroenterologist (oncologist according to indications).

3. In the treatment of the main disease of multiple myeloma and in the presence of high, medium, low levels antibodies of IgG to *H. pylori* infection, transfer from the intake of tableted steroid drugs to intravenous administration and prescribe eradication therapy during remission, according to indications.

4. To carry out autotransplantation of bone marrow for patients with multiple myeloma with *Helicobacter pylori* infection according to indications and in case of erosive, erosive-ulcerative gastritis, steroid ulcers, gastric and duodenal ulcers, autotransplantation of hematopoietic stem cells is contraindicated, to avoid complications.

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